

VALKYRIES

D1.11 Dashboard

Reference Number: D1.11

Ed/Rev: A/0

Main Contributor: INDRA

Other Contributors: TASSICA, PARTICLE

Date: 31/03/2023

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101020676

Editors

Name	Contact	Entity
Daniel Pablo Alonso	dpablo@indra.es	INDRA

Contributors

Name	Entity	Contribution
Marco Manso	PARTICLE	Review and inputs on the document.
Pedro Miguel	PARTICLE	Review and inputs on the document.
Alberto Montarelo	TASSICA	Review and inputs on the document.
Bassols Tayeda, Meritxell	INDRA	Review and inputs on the document.
Manuel Ocaña	INDRA	Quality review

Document Changes Record

Edit./Rev.	Date	Chapters	Reason for change
A/0	31/03/2023	All	Original Document

Content

- 1. Executive Summary 1
- 2. Identification 2
- 3. Requirements compliance matrix 3
- 4. Introduction 4
 - 4.1. Purpose of the document 4
 - 4.2. Scope of the document 4
 - 4.3. Document structure 4
- 5. Web-based tool menu..... 5
- 6. Tools 6
 - 6.1. VALKYRIES Dashboard (PARTICLE) 6
 - 6.2. TASSICA MCI 12
 - 6.3. iSafety..... 13
 - 6.4. HYBRID TWIN LAB..... 14
 - 6.5. PARTICLE.TALK..... 16
 - 6.6. AEODP (Aratos Earth Observation Data Platform)..... 17
 - 6.7. KYSTINFO 18

Tables

- Table 1 - WP1 Requirements Compliance Matrix 3

Figures

- Figure 1 - VALKYRIES website 5
- Figure 2 - VALKYRIES Tools Menu 5
- Figure 3 - AWARE Platform..... 7
- Figure 4 - VALKYRIES Dashboard 8
- Figure 5 - VALKYRIES Dashboard Incidents..... 8
- Figure 6 - Incidents and Organisations involved..... 9
- Figure 7 - VALKYRIES Dashboard Heatmap..... 9
- Figure 8 - VALKYRIES Dashboard Organisations 10
- Figure 9 - VALKYRIES Dashboard Assets 10
- Figure 10 - VALKYRIES Dashboard Victims..... 11
- Figure 11 - TASSICA MCI App..... 12
- Figure 12 - iSafety Map Monitor 13
- Figure 13 - Assets geolocalization and status..... 14
- Figure 14 - Event Communication and SIGRUN messages 14

Figure 15 - Web Streamed 3D COP Viewer 15

Figure 16 - Web Streamed 3D COP Viewer 15

Figure 17 - PARTICLE.TALK App 16

Figure 18 - AEODP (Aratos Earth Observation Data Platform) 17

Figure 19 - Avinet Kystinfo Platform..... 18

1. Executive Summary

This **D1.11. Dashboard** document presents the different features of the VALKYRIES Dashboard and the rest of the tools to be used in the project pilots. The main goal of this dashboard is to allow users and stakeholders to web-based interact with VALKYRIES applications. For this purpose, a menu was created under the name of Tools on the website where users can navigate through a drop-down list and find some details about VALKYRIES applications.

Until the end of the project, there will be modifications on the dashboard, tools, and their integration. This is the first and only version of the document but all these changes will be monthly reflected on the website.

2. Identification

Deliverable Title: Dashboard

Deliverable Id: D1.11

Deliverable Title Abbreviation: D1.11

Name of lead participant: INDRA

Name of Contributors: TASSICA, PARTICLE

Type: Demo (D)

Dissemination Level: Public (PU)

Proposed Classification Level: Non-Restricted

Reporting Conditions: Funding Requirement (FR)

Linked project Work Package: WP1

Linked project tasks: T1.4

Action: Design

Status: First Release, version A/0

Document Layout: Custom layout

Details: This deliverable D1.11 presents the different features of the VALKYRIES Dashboard. The main goal of this dashboard is to allow users and stakeholders to web-based interact with VALKYRIES applications. For this purpose, a menu was created under the name of Tools on the website. Users can navigate through a drop-down list and find some details about VALKYRIES applications.

3. Requirements compliance matrix

This deliverable demonstrates compliance with the requirement **REQ_BASE_T1.1_4** under the **task T1.4**. This Dashboard **SHOULD** allow users and stakeholder's interactions with VALKYRIES applications. For this purpose, a menu has been created within the website in which this dashboard and the rest of the tools that will be evaluated in the project appear.

ID	Priority	Traceability with Objectives	WBS Deliverables	Compliance	Results (Tested before and during the project pilots)
REQ_BASE_T1.1_4	P2	All	D1.11	RECOMMENDED	Design and implementation of a tool menu in our website which includes VALKYRIES Dashboard and tools.

Table 1 - WP1 Requirements Compliance Matrix

4. Introduction

4.1. Purpose of the document

This document is the first and only version of **D1.11 Dashboard**. The purpose of the document is to provide a description of the new VALKYRIES tool menu and a small description of each tool used. This document presents the results developed until M18 but some modifications will be made from now until the end of the project. These changes will be reflected directly on VALKYRIES website. It establishes all the applications that will be used in the project pilots.

4.2. Scope of the document

The scope of this document is to present the new website tool menu and a small description of the tools presented on the website. The document provides a tool menu structure based on the list of applications developed by VALKYRIES partners. These applications cover several operational services identified in the system architecture. There will be future integrations between the applications and VALKYRIES Dashboard.

4.3. Document structure

The document structure is the following:

1. **Chapter 1** is the Executive Summary and identification of the document.
2. **Chapter 2** indicates the identification data of the deliverable.
3. **Chapter 3** demonstrates compliance with the requirement REQ_BASE_T1.1_4 under the task T1.4. This requirement is related with D1.11.
4. **Chapter 4** is the current chapter.
5. **Chapter 5** presents the web-based tool menu that consists of a drop down with all VALKYRIES tools.
6. **Chapter 6** presents a description of each tool.

5. Web-based tool menu

A new menu has been created with the name of Tools on the website. The aim of this new menu is firstly to present the project tools to the public and secondly to allow users and stakeholders to web-based interact with VALKYRIES Dashboard. The website can be found at the following link <https://www.valkyries-h2020.eu/> and it will be monthly updated with additional information about tools. New tools will be added as the project progresses.

Figure 1 - VALKYRIES website

Figure 2 - VALKYRIES Tools Menu

6. Tools

This section presents **VALKYRIES applications** included in the new Tool menu on the website. All the technical details about the apps are well described in deliverable **D2.8 Architecture Design Document – A1** because this deliverable only includes general information about the tools. VALKYRIES Dashboard is described in more detail and all its functionalities are explained in the following section. New tools will be added as the project progresses and their characteristics will be added to the website.

All the applications are well connected based on APIs. The Application Program Interface (API) enables applications to exchange information and interact, and to establish a way, a channel, or other means, to exchange data without the need to rebuild the application entirely to match the other applications needs.

VALKYRIES applications cover various operational services identified in the system architecture and the list of tools is included below.

- **VALKYRIES Dashboard**
- **TASSICA MCI**
- **iSafety**
- **Hybrid Twin Lab**
- **PARTICLE.TALK**
- **AEODP (Aratos Earth Observation Data Platform)**
- **KYSTINFO**

6.1. VALKYRIES Dashboard

VALKYRIES project is developing a dashboard to represent the incidents, tasks, organisations involved, assets and victims in a MCI (Multi Casualty Incident) situation. This tool provides a view of existing incidents and resources mobilised (e.g., ambulances, first aid vehicles, personnel). It also allows assignments tracking and subsequent response updates representation: location of vehicles, casualty information (including EHR and vital signs if available) and estimated time of arrival (ETA). The Common Operational Picture (COP)/Dashboard that we are building is based on the AWARE tool developed by PARTICLE.

The **AWARE Platform** is a situational awareness tool for security practitioners and emergency response services, that provides an intuitive and comprehensive incident/event management system, displaying georeferenced events, associated with multimedia data (photos, videos, and text), that clearly identify the incident's type, severity, location, and time, as well as its status (open, closed, waiting for dispatch, dispatch sent).

The AWARE Platform enables the dispatch of assistance and the monitoring of the response effort, as well as the dissemination of notifications and alerts, through the interaction with accompanying mobile Apps. More information about the tool can be found [here](#).

Figure 3 - AWARE Platform

The AWARE Platform **includes two mobile applications:**

- **COP** is a mobile application for police officers that allows them to receive alerts, dispatch notifications, and use the smartphone to easily view and acknowledge reported incidents on a map. It allows police officers to upload the incident report, including additional evidence, such as photos and videos, directly to the AWARE Platform.
- **SAFER** is a mobile application for citizens to report incidents/crimes, using multi-channels such as messaging, images, video, and automatic location. Upholding responsible citizenship, SAFER includes social functions, such as one-to-one and one-to-many, thus supporting public alerting from public authorities on specific incidents.

Dashboard

VALKYRIES Dashboard principal view presents the following information:

- **Total number of victims and their status**
- **Total number of incidents and their status**
- **Information about the incident:**
 - **Dates of creation and update**
 - **Tasks**
 - **Personnel involved**

The images below show all the views available in VALKYRIES Dashboard. This first image shows the main dashboard panel where the total number of victims and the total number of incidents divided according to their status are represented. The tool can be accessed [here](#).

Figure 4 - VALKYRIES Dashboard

Incidents:

This second image represents the incident panel with a map showing their geolocation and the organisations involved. On the right side appears the list of emergency incidents and their creation and update dates. Zooming in on the image, it shows the location of the organisations and the incidents they are working on by means of a connecting line.

Figure 5 - VALKYRIES Dashboard Incidents

Figure 6 - Incidents and Organisations involved

Heatmap and Organisations:

The following images represent a heatmap showing the magnitude of the incidents based on a colour code and a map with the organizations' location. The variation in colour gives obvious visual cues to users and stakeholders about how the multi-casualty incident is clustered and varies over space. On the other hand, the organisation panel presents a short description of the organisation and its functions, as well as the units involved in the incidents.

Figure 7 - VALKYRIES Dashboard Heatmap

Figure 8 - VALKYRIES Dashboard Organisations

Assets and Victims:

These images represent the last two panels from VALKYRIES Dashboard. The first image represents assets and staff location on the map and the other one the health status of all the victims.

Figure 9 - VALKYRIES Dashboard Assets

Figure 10 - VALKYRIES Dashboard Victims

6.2. TASSICA MCI

TASSICA MCI is a native Android app designed to support first responders in an MCI declaration, from the first info about MCI place (geo coordinates, photos, CBRN risk, etc) to victims first and second triage data (no personal information is collected). TASSICA app can be downloaded from [here](#).

User can organize information of the victims in a context of overflowing demand for assistance and maximum stress, facilitating rapid, effective, continuous, quality assistance to victims, and also send all collected data to the control centre.

As it is a **TASSICA proprietary solution**, the tool has not been uploaded to be able to web-based interact with TASSICA MCI, but it is an Android App available at Google Play Store. The corresponding section has been created in the website tools menu. Work is being done to integrate the tool with VALKYRIES Dashboard focused on the pilots.

Figure 11 - TASSICA MCI App

6.3. iSafety

iSAFETY is an INTEGRATED INCIDENT & EMERGENCY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM to deploy Call Receiving, Incident Dispatch and Tracking, Radio/Voice communications integration and Reports, based on Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and Automatic Vehicle Location (AVL). iSafety manages and facilitates the daily operations and decision-making, offering at every moment the best response options to each situation, assisting the operators and providing real time information. **It is a modular software application to manage:**

- **Incident Reception** (Receives, locates, and classifies incidents)
- **Dispatch and Tracking** (Best resource proposal)
- **Communications** (Controls the tactical situation)
- **Reports** (Provides executive information)

As it is an **Indra proprietary solution**, the tool has not been uploaded to be able to web-based interact with iSafety, but the corresponding section has been created in the website tools menu. Work is being done to integrate the tool with VALKYRIES Dashboard focused on the pilots. More information about the tool can be found [here](#).

Figure 12 - iSafety Map Monitor

6.4. Hybrid Twin Lab

Hybrid Twin Lab (HTL) is a synthetic and immersive tool for integrate, generate, and manage mixed scenarios composed of real, simulated, or virtualized assets (digital twins) in a multi-domain environment based on real or synthetic data. HTL in VALKYRIES operates as a technology enabler, a platform with the ability to plan and provide different scenarios to other systems. It provides a test bed suitable to integrate and test different components, capabilities, or communication ontologies in a common and widely configurable environment.

Figure 13 - Assets geolocalisation and status

It supports the possibility to switch between different augmented dimensions, based on the complexity of the information to be visualized. The tool makes it possible to switch between the physical and cyber domain at any time and also provides analysis capacity, KPIs (Key Performance Indicator) and statistics reporting with all the data generated during scenarios execution, additionally allowing a later debriefing.

Figure 14 - Event Communication and SIGRUN messages

It is also considered a system integrator, because HTL allows different environments generated by various systems to share a common context with full interaction and communication between all the assets, independently of their origin or location in the real or cyber realities. A complete simulation and emulation of assets through the aggregation of other assets or functional components can be performed by HTL. It offers a complete integrated environment supported by its own HMI (Human Machine Interface), to visualize and interact with the scenario, based on intuitive controls and maps.

Figure 15 - Web Streamed 3D COP Viewer

As it is an **Indra proprietary solution**, the tool has not been uploaded to be able to web-based interact with HTL, but the corresponding section has been created in the website tools menu. Work is being done to integrate the tool with VALKYRIES Dashboard focused on the pilots.

Figure 16 - Web Streamed 3D COP Viewer

6.5. PARTICLE.TALK

PARTICLE.TALK is a modern IP-based private digital communications service supporting multi-protocols for chat, audio, and video communication. Supports presence information, send, and read receipt, and message notifications.

This tool also supports document exchange (e.g., best practices and instructions in case of incident) and notifications (for issuing alerts) and its servers can be installed at the customer premisses or at PARTICLE cloud servers. Regardless, customers have full control of communications and content.

As it is a **PARTICLE proprietary solution**, the tool has not been uploaded to be able to web-based interact with [PARTICLE.TALK](#), but the corresponding section has been created in the website tools menu. Work is being done to integrate the tool with VALKYRIES Dashboard focused on the pilots.

Figure 17 - PARTICLE.TALK App

6.6. AEODP

The [AEODP](#) Platform provides useful information in real or near real time. It provides users with useful insights and information, in the form of layers on a map, by analysing satellite data. AEODP supports collection of Satellite data from sensors SAR (Synthetic Aperture Radar). This feature provides high resolution images even during night-time or in cloudy areas. Also allows detection of small movements on the ground and effective land and water monitoring.

[AEODP](#) is an integration of different modern technologies and all available open satellite data "all-in-one place" through Satellite Imaging and Observation, Internet of Things, Big Data Analysis, AI, Blockchain Technologies. It can be accessed also as a service by everywhere, anytime, all the time with maximum security and ease of use.

This tool has the following characteristics:

- **Analyse Satellite Data from all available commercial and open sources.**
- **Provide Near Real-Time Information.**
- **Planning, prevention, and damage assessment.**
- **A Geo intelligence Platform providing timely alerts.**
- **Data Fusion from Space – Air – Ground**
- **Low Cost, Effective Solution (available as a service)**
- **Easy to use by experts and non-experts**

As it is an **Aratos proprietary solution**, the tool has not been uploaded to be able to web-based interact with AEODP, but the corresponding section has been created in the website tools menu. Work is being done to integrate the tool with VALKYRIES Dashboard focused on the pilots.

Figure 18 - AEODP

6.7. KYSTINFO

KYSTINFO is a web based layered sea-map system created by Avinet where many different layers with information can be activated and updated real-time by the coastal administration, its partners, and registered users. Many layers are freely available by default, some examples are navigational installations, anchorage areas, harbours, marine charts, depth maps, real-time and historical AIS vessel data, hazardous areas, accident frequency and meteorological data (wind, wave high and direction, precipitation, currents). The tool can be accessed [here](#) and it will be used for the last pilot in Norway.

Information related to preparedness and environmental concerns are also available by default. This includes information about ports of refuge, areas with protected species, vulnerable areas, environmental management zones, storage locations and lists of available equipment. Users can upload data such as images, KSAT satellite pictures, documents, and files. The **KYSTINFO system** has many base maps available and has functionality to upload your own map data or map data from other sources.

Figure 19 - Avinet Kystinfo Platform

6.8. Annex A – Glossary

Category	Description
AEODP	Aratos Earth Observation Data Platform
API	Application Program Interface
AVL	Automatic Vehicle Locator
CBRN	Chemical, Biological, Radiological, and Nuclear
COP	Common Operational Picture
EHR	Electronic Health Record
ETA	Estimated Time of Arrival
GIS	Geographic Information Systems
HMI	Human Machine Interface
HTL	Hybrid Twin Lab
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MCI	Multi-Casualty Incident
SAR	Synthetic Aperture Radar

Table 2 - Glossary